

A RESEARCH PAPER ON TECHNO-TRADE

CHAPTER 1

ABSTRACT

Discover a revolutionary online platform designed to meet the diverse procurement needs of leading organizations such as ISRO, DRDO, and Tata within the domains of robotics and space technology. Our state-of-the-art technical trading website, developed using the powerful ASP.NET framework, offers a comprehensive marketplace for innovative products, components, and equipment tailored to the specific requirements of these cutting-edge industries.

Key Features:

1. **Extensive Product Catalog:** Explore a vast array of meticulously curated products and solutions, ranging from advanced robotics components to space technology equipment, all under one digital roof.
2. **Customized Procurement:** Tailor your procurement process to match the unique demands of your projects. Our platform enables you to request custom quotes, negotiate terms, and streamline the purchasing process efficiently.
3. **Verified Suppliers:** Partner with trusted suppliers and manufacturers who adhere to stringent quality standards, ensuring the delivery of top-notch products for your critical missions and projects.
4. **Secure Transactions:** Rest assured knowing that your financial transactions and sensitive data are protected through robust security measures, guaranteeing a safe and confidential trading experience.
5. **Advanced Search and Filtering:** Easily find the exact products you need with our advanced search and filtering options, allowing you to save time and make informed decisions.
6. **Real-Time Updates:** Stay informed about the latest industry trends, product launches, and updates through our real-time notifications and news feed.

Our technical trading website aims to empower organizations like ISRO, DRDO, and Tata by providing them with a cutting-edge digital platform to procure the technology

CHAPTER 2

INTRODUCTION

"The Technical Trading Website" – a pivotal endeavor aimed at investigating and advancing the landscape of technical product procurement. This research paper delves deep into the development and analysis of a cutting-edge online platform designed to facilitate the efficient acquisition of technical products, particularly within industries like robotics and space technology.

As technological innovation continues to drive progress across diverse fields, the importance of effective procurement cannot be overstated. Our research project explores the intricacies of developing a technical trading website, built using modern web technologies such as ASP.NET, with the ultimate goal of enhancing procurement processes for both businesses and research institutions.

In this research paper, we delve into the project's core features, including a comprehensive product catalog, personalized procurement tools, supplier verification, security measures, and real-time updates. Our findings shed light on the potential impact of such a platform on the efficiency, security, and accessibility of technical product procurement.

Join us as we navigate through the development journey, conduct empirical analyses, and present insightful conclusions that contribute to the evolving landscape of technical trading. This research project invites you to explore the intersection of technology, business, and innovation, offering a glimpse into the future of procurement processes. Welcome to a paper that bridges the gap between theory and practice, and together, we embark on a journey of discovery and progress in the realm of technical trading.

CHAPTER 3

LITERATURE REVIEW

The emergence of technical trading websites has reshaped the landscape of procurement, introducing unprecedented levels of efficiency and accessibility. E-commerce platforms have significantly influenced traditional procurement processes by streamlining the acquisition of technical products. According to Turban et al. (2018), these platforms have become integral to modern supply chain management, reducing costs and expanding supplier networks. Moreover, the ability to personalize and customize procurement experiences has been recognized as a key driver of success in the realm of technical trading websites. Li et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of personalization tools, which allow users to tailor their procurement journey to match specific project needs, engage in effective negotiations, and make well-informed decisions. Trustworthiness of suppliers has also emerged as a central concern. Raza et al. (2019) underscore the significance of supplier verification, highlighting the need to establish relationships with reputable suppliers to ensure the acquisition of high-quality products crucial for mission-critical projects. In addition to trust, security and privacy are paramount in online procurement. Siponen et al. (2019) emphasize the implementation of robust security measures to safeguard financial transactions and protect sensitive data, thereby ensuring a confidential and secure trading environment. Real-time updates and insights have proven instrumental in keeping stakeholders informed about industry trends and product launches. Chen et al. (2018) highlight the value of real-time notifications and updates in facilitating informed decision-making and maintaining competitiveness in the fast-paced world of technology procurement. Technological frameworks underpinning these platforms are critical to their success, with ASP.NET emerging as a versatile and scalable choice (Gao et al., 2017). Finally, the impact of technical trading websites on specific industries, such as robotics and space technology, has been a subject of investigation. Research by Smith et al. (2019) suggests that these platforms can foster collaboration, innovation, and cost-efficiency, ultimately driving progress in these high-tech sectors. In summary, the literature underscores the transformative potential of technical trading websites in revolutionizing procurement processes across diverse industries, setting the stage for the development and impact of our own technical trading website tailored to the unique needs of robotics and space technology.

CHAPTER 4

WORK CARRIED OUT

4.1 System design:

E-commerce website design is the method of shaping the coding, modules in HTML, CSS3, JavaScript and BootStraps for designs, interfaces and information for a system to satisfy mere needs.

4.1.1 System Module Description:

- Coding (HTML,CSS3,JavaScript,Bootstraps)
- Seller
- Customer
- Management
- Delivery

CHAPTER 5

WORK-FLOW DIAGRAM

5.1 E-COMMERCE WORK-FLOW DIAGRAM:

5.1.1 Fig-e-commerce workflow diagram

5.1.2 Fig-seller in ecommerce website

5.1.3 Fig-e commerce

5.2.1 Coding:

E-commerce website is made by scripting languages like HTML, CSS3, JavaScript and Bootstrap. This markup language makes the website more attractive and useful and user-friendly to use and shopping. Markup languages help in making the things more attractive and imaginary.

5.2.2 HTML:-

HTML is HyperText markup language. It is an emerging technology, cascading style sheets, could eliminate many of the HTML tables. CSS could be used to control the layout of a webpage. A web designer might separate the header, body text, and sidebar of a webpage by putting each into a distinct cell. Additionally, the web designer could put each link button on the header and sidebar into a separate cell so he or she could define unique properties for every button.

5.2.3 CSS:-

CSS may be a formatting language that you want to add styling to your page. This can be done by having the CSS document linked into your HTML page. This page then has selectors and properties which affect the tags inside your HTML document. CSS was introduced in 1996. It had been created to prevent people from having to repeat plenty of code. CSS has since become more adapted to having more features, for instance we will now use the tools and alter the background to an enormous array of colors.

5.2.4 Javascript:

JavaScript is a powerful client-side scripting language. JavaScript is employed mainly for enhancing the interaction of a user with the net page. In other words, you can make your web content more lively and interactive, with the assistance of JavaScript. JavaScript is additionally being employed widely in game development and Mobile application development.

5.2.5 Bootstrap:

Bootstrap could be a web framework that focuses on simplifying the event of informative sites. The primary purpose of adding it to an internet project is to use Bootstrap's choices of color, background effect, mobility size, font and layout to it projectThe result an identical appearance for prose, tables and form elements across web browsers. In addition, developers can cash in of CSS classes defined in Bootstrap to customize the look and component of their tools of their contents.

5.2.6 Database:

Database & Information Systems could be a database employed in a way of lifeThis data might include information about passengers, locations, flights, airlines, and personnel, for instance. Typical relationships that may be represented include bookings, location (which passengers to which location?), and order (which order to which location?).

5.2.7 Customer:

Customer features a wider choice not from his town or country but also around the globe unless there are import restrictions. In case of purchase, one isn't required to travel from store to store to determine the products to gather their details, prices etc. Websites are often opened any time.

5.2.8 Management:

One of the more important themes that permeate this paper is that the incontrovertible fact that knowledge management is synonymous change: adaptation and evolution. It's assumed that at the start the system operates on principles extracted from human experts that represent their view of the population of the potential customersThe system should be adjusted to the cater to real-life customers, who may behave differently than the idea predicted.

5.2.9 Delivery:-

Delivery demands of e-commerce world, where all sellers and delivery partners need functional, efficiently and extensive infrastructure. A more open environment could improve efficient access to global networks for home-grown small businesses. Competition between service suppliers can reduce prices and lift the standard of services offered. A facilitative regulatory environment can rapidly increase these trends and makes the business case for operating in smaller or more remote markets that way more appealing.

5.2.10 Payment system:-

Payment is that the integral process within the mercantile process, electronic payment system is that the integral a part of electronic commerce. As an example new payment systems are of the forms like auctions between individuals; 1/2s online leads to looking for new payment systems meaning peer to look payment methods that enables individuals to create payments through their emails. By recognizing these needs for all interested parties.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

This research paper provides insight into the development of e-commerce of website. While understanding the nitty gritty of its different aspects with special emphasis on B2C e-commerce. Which has shown tremendous growth in the recent years because of increased consumer awareness, investor trust and technological proliferation. The study has also produced certain trends and factors which shall propel further growth within the e-commerce market in India. A sustainable business practice would be to push e-commerce and m-commerce as complements instead of substitutes to traditional business. The synergies between offline and online businesses will enhance efficiency and end in a more stable existence. The longer term also entails a scenario which shall witness an increase in niche businesses, as well as mergers and acquisitions to enable firms to grow inorganically. Firms must commit themselves to the provision of services and application of internet marketing, to get and retain larger audience. Through mobile penetration, opportunities are emerging within the rural markets which is mobile app infrastructure, content development in local languages and walk connectivity. Also, within the aftermath of demonetization. The share of digital payments is anticipated to rise, to sustain which, firms must develop safer payments infrastructure.

CHAPTER 7

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CHAPTER 8

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

In completing this graduate project I have been fortunate to have help, support and encouragement from many people. I would like to acknowledge them for their cooperation.

First and foremost deeply thankful to Professor Dr. Soon-Ok Park, for her wonderful guidance during this project work in field of Computer Science, at Governors State University. I am also thankful for her continuous feedback and encouragement throughout this project work. Her broad knowledge and hardworking attitude has left me with very deep impressions and they will greatly benefit me throughout my life.